

Impact of Celebrities on Consumer Buying Behaviour

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Abstract: Nowadays marketers are using celebrities for promoting the brand and targeting the consumers that are attracted by famous people who are advertising the products. The aim of this research is to identify and critically analyze the importance of celebrity endorsement and the impact on consumer buying behavior. The previous research has shown that star endorsement strategy is used by multiple top brands worldwide such as Nike, Pepsi, Dior, Calvin Klein to generate higher sales and to build credibility to the brand offer. Furthermore, this study focuses on examining the perception of consumers about celebrity endorsements, examining the celebrity attributes likely to influence consumer purchase intentions and finally the impact of celebrity endorsements on their Consumer Buying Behavior. Recommendation for companies regarding selection of celebrities is that companies should do that after ensure that the celebrities' image and overall personalities must match with the brand personality.

Keywords: Celebrity Endorsement, Consumer Buying Behavior.

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I. INTRODUCTION

According to Drenik (2022) celebrities' endorsement increases brand awareness and brings value to the business but also can have a negative impact on consumer buying decisions. Despite several benefits' celebrity endorsement can affect the consumer purchase decision by advertising the wrong message and the endorsed product. To make these strategies successful, marketers employ famous celebrities because celebrities have the power to create a greater impact on the consumers' buying behavior. Since some of the celebrities have charismatic personalities and they enjoy public recognition because they possess distinctive qualities like trustworthiness and attractiveness. Many big brands make use of the concept of celebrity endorsement as marketing communication tools. The current investigation is quite significant because it focuses on showing the changes in consumer buying behavior when an organization uses celebrity endorsement for the promotion of products and services

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the work is the means and scientific research methods that were used: scientific knowledge, explanation, scientific observation, induction and deduction, description and comparison. Consumer demands are continuously changing, and marketers are using different methods to target emotionally the audience. There has been an increase in celebrity endorsement in marketing

advertisements because of influences of consumers brand choices and behaviors. Brand communication messages delivered by celebrities create attention and higher appeal as one of the powerful tools adopted by companies to attract consumers who want to have similar status, values, and lifestyle.

III. CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENT MODELS

Consumer demands are continuously changing, and marketers are using different methods to target emotionally the audience. There has been an increase in celebrity endorsement in marketing advertisements because of influences of consumers brand choices and behaviors. (Olenski, 2023). According to Masood (2023) a celebrity is defined as a popular person such as a movie star, TV personalities, artists, models, or sports icons that provide a very common type of reference group appeal. Moreover, huge numbers of consumer groups are following the celebrities on social media, Instagram, YouTube or Facebook. (Hashaw, 2022). Brand communication message delivered by celebrities create attention and higher appeal as one of the powerful tool adopted by companies to attract consumers who wants to have similar status, values, and lifestyle. (Glenn Vo, 2021). Previous research has shown that celebrities can have a positive and negative impact on consumers who are purchasing the endorsed products, such as food, drinks, or fashion items. (Masood, 2020).

According to Solomon (2012) marketers are applying different strategies that appeal to one or more groups of consumers depending on age, gender, social class, race and ethnicity, geography, and lifestyle, by developing a product to attract a particular core audience. Although many consumers are not realizing how marketers are using celebrities to influence their preferences for movie, food, the latest fashions in clothing or decorating products through popular personalities that are effective spokes characters for the products they represent. (Pradeep, 2021). Others research has claimed that consumers often buy products not for what they want but for what they mean, people will select a brand that has a celebrity consistent with their underlying needs. For example, consumers are choosing Nike instead of Reebok because of running faster. Also, Nike created a high marketed brand by using athletes to build costumers relationship (Masood, 2021). Marketers are using famous people to maximize the consumer attitude by two important source characteristics which are credibility and attractiveness. (Ryan & Jones, 2022).

➤ *Source Credibility Model*

Solomon (2012) states that credibility model refers to objectivity or trustworthiness of a source. Research studies show that a source with a high credibility leads to a higher level of consumer buying behavior than a source with low credibility. (Assael, 2019). Marketers are using celebrities who have popular credibility among the consumers to gain an audience and to make high profit. (Masood, 2020).

➤ *Source of Attractiveness Model*

According to Solomon (2012) source of attractiveness has emanated from people with physical appearance, personality, or social status. Almost all marketing campaigns are using beautiful people that are trying to persuade consumers to buy products that do not necessarily need to be purchased. (Parkin, 2019). Some evidence indicates that consumers pay more attention to attractive models and can create positive attitudes and feelings through this type of advertising which influences the purchase intentions. (Pradeep, 2019). Advertisers believe in celebrity endorsers effectiveness because of increasing company image and brand attitude by choosing the right personality depending on what meaning the product should convey. (Masood, 2020). Assael (2019) argues that star power works because it symbolizes different categories such as status, social class, gender, and even personality type. For marketing campaigns to be effective the endorser must have a good reputation and a popular image to attract the consumers that often refers to singers such as Shakira, Beyoncé, or Madonna. (Ryan & Jones, 2020).

IV. S-O-R THEORY

Solomon (2012) states that S-O-R Theory, also known as Stimulus-Organism-Response, is a frame used to analyze the feelings and consumer behavior caused by external environment. The Stimulus-Organism-Response is based on the internal feelings or behavior of an organism (person) that can be conscious or unconscious. (Ryan & Jones, 2020). According to Glen Vo (2021) the S-O-R Theory is applied

by marketers by using celebrities as an emotional trigger to affect the consumer buyer's decision. In this study there are two stimuli which will affect the internal state of the consumer: advertisements and publicity.

The organism represents the emotional response of the consumers toward the brand and celebrities. (Medina, 2019). The previous studies describe stimulus response as an impact on consumer buyers' decisions that can have a positive or negative effect. (Parkin, 2019).

V. BALANCE THEORY

According to Solomon (2012) the Balance theory refers to elements that consumer might perceive as a belonging together. These perceptions can be positive or negative and can be associated with positively valued objects. Also, consumers can form strong relations with a product from a certain brand. (Assael, 2019). Balance theory is popular for celebrity endorsement by creating a positive attitude between the product and the consumers. (e.g., buying fashionable clothes or driving a high-performance car). However, consumer negative attitude towards celebrities can negatively affect the consumer decision regarding the products. (Pradeep, 2019).

According to Adedeji (2021), celebrity endorsement is one of the effective strategies which helps in gaining brand loyalty and consumer interest. Through celebrity endorsement, companies can increase awareness of advertisement and also create positive feelings towards the brand. Celebrity endorsement helps in increasing the profitability and sale of business due to which fashion industry can gain competitive advantage in market. Using a celebrity can help in differentiating the brand from competitors. The effectiveness of celebrity endorsement can be measured according to the five dimensions such as attention grabbing, personality and appeal, positive feeling towards the advertisement, purchase intention and high recall rates. In order to measure the effectiveness, attractiveness and credibility of certain celebrities it is necessary to identify the active followers of the celebrities on social media platform. Through understanding and identifying the active followers, companies can determine their recognition in the market and also make decisions to endorse the celebrity for particular product and services. (Strunk, 2019). Thus, it is important for organizations to hire renowned and recognize celebrities so that they can improve the sales and profitability of business by promoting products and services. Credibility of celebrity also influences the attitude of consumers by affecting the confidence of consumers and changing their perception related to the products and services of brand. While endorsing celebrities, it is important to determine the tag line which is suitable according to the personality of celebrity so that they can encourage customers to buy the products of brand. In order to measure the effectiveness of celebrities, companies must focus on identifying how much they are selling in the duration of particular celebrity. Thus, the fashion industry must focus on hiring renowned celebrities as if they choose the person who is not accepted by the public can influence

the sales and performance of business due to which fashion companies have to face severe loss. However, it is important for organization to investigate the relationship between endorsement of celebrity and credibility perceived by consumers (Yang and Sia, 2020). While measuring the effectiveness of celebrity, companies must focus on sales revenue, the power of product and the acceptance of products. When people accept the product, it helps in enhancing the profitability and growth of business. Public generally know the celebrity rather than knowing the product which they endorsed. Through celebrity endorsement, companies can grab the attention of customers and also attract more and more people towards the brand in order to gain a competitive edge. Therefore, celebrity endorsement generally creates an impact on the consumer's purchase intention as if they feel good towards the celebrity, the purchase intention increases. In today's world digital media plays an important role due to which fashion companies focus on identifying the ways to use brand promoting celebrities in online methods.

VI. DISCUSSION

This research analysed three different theories to identify which one can contribute to an effective celebrity endorsement strategy. The first theory discussed is the Source of physical attractiveness and credibility which has shown that increases trustworthiness and degree of confidence among the students who are buying endorsed products from majority of brands that are using celebrities. Furthermore, the Companies should focus on physical attractiveness of the celebrity in order to attract the consumers and increase their revenues. S-O-R theory is perceived as the most effective strategy related to celebrity endorsement products that can influence the decision-making process for a particular brand that is promoting a famous celebrity who can affect the purchase intentions for a particular product that has a high impact on attitudes towards the advertisement than the non-celebrity. The third model analyzed is the Balance theory that also shows that can have a positive or negative impact on consumers depending on their perception of certain celebrities that affects their attitudes and intentions by the distinctiveness of the endorser. Additionally, the research shows that sport apparel endorsed products are mostly purchased by the students who are influenced by celebrities' trustworthiness and expertise.

This research also provides guidelines for companies to identify the key success factors of brand endorsement when targeting students. Moreover, the businesses should emphasis on the product first and then can decide for a brand endorser by choosing the right celebrity which consumers highly identify themselves with the spokesperson.

From the analysis of the data previously presented it can be concluded that celebrity endorsement plays an important role in improving the profitability and sale of business among the student market segments. It is the responsibility of fashion organization to hire the celebrity

who have potential to improve the brand awareness and reputation of company due to which company can attract maximum number of customers towards the brand. Students recognize that there are various benefits of celebrity endorsement within business as they help in generating more revenue, improving the sale, enhancing the reputation, building credibility and provides opportunity to expand business in new market. Thus, celebrity endorsement helps in attracting more and more people towards the brand due to which organization can gain competitive edge in market.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In order to promote the products and services of fashion industry, organization focuses on hiring celebrities who like to remain trendy with the fashion and can influence the perception of customer to buy the product. If a company is selling clothes of young people, it is important to hire the celebrity who can engage and influence the purchase decision of youngsters. Students generally like to purchase the product of brand which is endorsed by their favorite celebrity. There is effective use of celebrity endorsers within the fashion industry such as they improve sales, build positive brand image, make advertisement credible and also enhance customer recognition. The products which grab the attention of customers are sports apparel, technology products, cosmetic products, clothing, and footwear. Customers generally make perceptions about the products and services while making purchase decision such as they identify the worth of product, determine the reputation, and also focuses on identifying the risk while purchasing the product. This study will help the companies by providing them with the most important characteristics for successful brand endorsement. As a result, the combination of all endorsement theories is the most effective way to enhance consumer attitude and perception.

RECOMMENDATION

- From the above information it is recommended that organizations must focus on identifying the right celebrity according to their budget and market presence so that they can promote the products and services in an effective and successful manner.
- In order to increase the profitability and growth of business, it is important to offer high quality products and services to its customer as it helps in building trust among audiences due to which they become loyal.

For increasing the sale of products through celebrity endorsement, fashion organizations can focus on implementing marketing tactics such as offering autographs and signature of their favorite celebrity while purchasing the product. The company can also provide an opportunity to consumers to avail selfie with the celebrity who is endorsing the product as it helps in increasing the sale and profitability of business.

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